

Towards Operational Awareness in Fuzzy Logic Uncertainty Management

To be, or not to be: that is the question:
(Shakespeare W., 1600 ca.)

Abstract

A seemingly simple problem. Decide between **A** and **B**. That this problem is not simple it is known since ancient times, one thinks, for example to the famous "*Buridan's ass*". The objective of this article is to reveal through the discussion of a metaphor, discussion that we can think as a *Gedankenexperiment*, some little known, neither frequently adressed, topics in discussing dilemma. Furthermore it will be attempted to provide some "operational awareness" for this type of situation. Dispelling some clichés.

Keywords

Alternatives, Operational awareness, Decision, Dilemma, Dispute, Fuzzy Logic, Gedankenexperiment, Uncertainty, Metaphore.

Introduction

A seemingly simple problem. Deciding between **A** and **B**. It is known since ancient times that this problem is not simple, and not only because of the famous monologue reported in the epigraph. An example is the famous "*Buridan's ass*". The example of the donkey who starved to death for not being able to decide which graze "*between two fields, equally brought to both*" (*Leibniz G., 1686*), however, it is mis-attributed to Jean Buridan (1290-1358). Buridan himself in fact never used this *metaphor*, which still remain interesting, so much so that the same Leibniz (*ibid.*) wrote about it. Incidentally, perhaps it is exactly to him that we owe that erroneous attribution because, in his *Theodicy (ibid.)* he refers to the donkey *metaphor* as the "*Buridan's ass*". [Key words and words which are used herein with slightly different meaning from the usual one are in *italics*, and the *first time* they are mentioned in *italics and underlined*. This is to distinguish the cases in which that term is used in common sense or not]

In fact, the *dilemma* is a concept hiding a profound challenge to our ability to reason from both the philosophical and psychological point of view.

The objective of this article is to reveal, through the discussion of a *metaphor*, discussion that we can think taking place as a *Gedankenexperiment* (thought experiment), some little-known and not frequently treated aspects of *dilemma* situations on one end, and to provide *operational awareness* (*Ceccato S., 1962/1964*) for this type of situation on the other. It will be demonstrated that some implicit assumptions are not always true. In simple words there will be debunked some common myths. It will made express reference to *Fuzzy logic* but no prior knowledge of it is actually needed.

We start by analyzing the simple **Figure 1** in which two options **A** or **B** which we can think either as two *options* that we are considering ourselves, in which case we speak of a *dilemma*, or two *options*, referring to **two different entities**, in which case we will refer to it as a *dispute*.

What will be said is, in most cases, valid both for the *dilemma* and for the *dispute* case and there will be used, in the following, indifferently, metaphors that refer to one or the other situation, depending on the case.

Tertium datur – first implicit assumption

Furthermore, on the contrary to *Buridan's ass* which could decide only between **A** or **B**, *tertium non datur*, we will discuss here a more general case in which **A** and **B** belong to a *continuum* (**Figure 2**). Take for example the case of a *dispute*, frequently in common reasoning, but also in the mathematical one, the *value* of a *decision* is judged based on the simple *distance* by either *alternative*. This would seem to be the most reasonable approach and, in fact, is precisely what is commonly used..

The closer to me the better - second implicit assumption

In order to achieve greater *operational awareness* about the consequences of this way of thinking, also in relation to what will be said, we can consider making this explicit relation between the *decision value* and the *decision* itself, as illustrated in **Figure 3**. Basically, it is assumed, in this case, the *value* of the *decision*, a simple linear relationship (with unit coefficient) between the distance of the decision by the two horns of the dilemma and the value thereof. In simple terms: a pure and simple direct proportionality with unit rate. The closer the better.

It should be noted that the *value* "seen" by A is not equal *value* "seen" by B.

The implicit assumptions – Common Places to dispel

It is important to note that, in general, we make the following implicit assumptions (corresponding to their relevant common places that will try to dispel, the first being the aforementioned *tertium not datur* and the second that of *the closer to me the better*, cited too) and that is that

- what one part earns is necessarily lost by the other (*mors tua vita mea* third cliché).

but also that

- "*in medio stat virtus*" (fourth cliché), as conventional wisdom also would suggest.

But things really are (only) so? Without entering unnecessarily into the details of *fuzzy logic* (Zadeh L., 1965), (Fortemps P., Roubens M., 1996), (Mamdani E., Assilina S., 1975), we can replace with the straight lines of **Figure 3** the curves of **Figure 4**.

Note that the curves of **Figure 4** relate to a more general case than the one now under consideration and precisely they involve the case in which the two alternatives are not of the same weight, incidentally therefore recalling the solution that Leibniz seemed to suggest in his *Theodicy* (*ibid.*) to the Buridan's ass problem, that is that no two situations are really equivalent..

In fact, much of the reasoning still holds, and without loss of generality, also using figures simpler than those reported in **Figure 4**. These figures make use of so-called "*tent functions*", well known for example in the field of deterministic chaos, and which are substantially triangles (without the base) or trapezoids (without the main base). Therefore, for simplicity, in the following, we will use them, almost always.

Now that we have introduced the problem in general terms, the basic question to which we will try to answer below is as follows:

Which are essentially the *operations* people do to deal with a *dilemma*?

Anticipating a part of the answer, we can say that the key to finding a simple but general description of these operations can be found in promoting uncertainty from the status of **problem** to the one of **instrument of knowledge**.

In order to illustrate this statement, which at first glance may seem paradoxical, we can explore a *metaphor* and we know from Lakoff and Núñez (Lakoff G., Núñez R., 2000) how important *metaphors* (and *conceptual mixtures*) are also in mathematical reasoning. The exploration of this *metaphor* is in fact our Gedankenexperiment.

Figure 3

Figure 4

The metaphor, which will be here the one of a hypothetical *dispute* (integrated here and there with the similar one of the *dilemma*), will be illustrated by putting in relation, not any more the simple distance between the two positions, as already discussed for the cases of **Figures 2** and **3**, but rather the mutual *overlap* of the *uncertainties* and that we can think represented by the functions of **Figure 4** and by the simplifications of the subsequent figures.

Here we address directly the question of the *meaning* of *uncertainty*, since this meaning will emerge, at least in part, from the discussion of *operations* and *metaphors* illustrated and discussed below.

We mention only that the *value* of the *decision*, represented mathematically by the *value* of the function **A** or **B** can be interpreted, in the *metaphors* that follow as the " *impact* 'or simply the' " *interest*", that the *parts* have to the particular decision **A** or **B** (*dispute*). Or the " *value*" that we give ourselves from our *point of view A* or from our *point of view B* to that particular *decision* (*dilemma*).

The *metaphor* of the *dispute* will be illustrated by discussing the relationship that we have, for every possible *decision*, for the values which **A** and **B**, subjectively attributed to it. Mathematically, the *values* of the functions **A** and **B**.

Technically the trajectory that illustrates this relationship, which can be constructed as shown graphically in detail in **Figure 5A**, is obtained by scanning from left to right the range of interest, as indeed we will also do for the other cases reported in the following. It should be noted incidentally that scanning also the entire axis would obtained the same results as the functions are different from zero only for the mentioned interval.

Checking the third implicit assumption - is always only *mors tua vita mea*?

We start from the simple **Case A** of **Figure 5**. In this case, the *alternatives* (substantially) coincide and we will have only one possibility, namely the ability to increase together or decrease together (the *value* of the *decision*). In the case of a *dispute* we can think of it as the case in which we do (essentially) agree.

Case A –COvariance Only

Figure 5

Note that so far, and will be so in much of the following, functions will be **symmetrical**

with respect to a value which coincides with the **maximum** value (normalized to 1 for simplicity), "in a manner that everything is equal and similar on the one hand and the other, as an ellipse or any flat figures, the category of what I call 'anfidestre' " always in the words of the same *Leibniz* (*ibid.*). But this may not always be the case, indeed for *Leibniz* (*ibid.*) it is **never** the case. Although many of the results remain valid also in the case of functions that are not symmetrical with respect to this **maximum value**, in order to obtain results more general it will be however illustrated, also a different situation. We will illustrate for the moment the metaphor mainly through symmetric functions for ease of illustration graphics and conceptual.

Please note, incidentally, however, that the trajectory that illustrates the **Case A** of **Figure 5**, and that we can call the one of *covariance* only, remains the same, namely a simple segment of a straight line at 45 degrees, even in the case where the *tent functions* were to be replaced with more general functions, such as those of **Figure 4**. In the case where the relative heights were different this would only change the inclination but the topology would remain the same (ie the path would always be a line segment).

We come to analyze the more general case, which is then also one that allows, among other things, to highlight some **common places** deriving precisely from lack of *operational awareness* in situations of this type.

In **Figure 6** we can distinguish 5 traits distinct for the trajectory that is, in this case, a complete cycle. These 5 strokes correspond to as many corresponding distinct phases:

1. First we have a phase in which the solution has "interest" only for the first subject (only the value of the function **A** is $\neq 0$ in this range). We can think metaphorically, in a dispute, at this early stage, it is still taking no account of the other party (or of the other hypothesis in the case of the dilemma) that's why we have indicated, in the following, this time as a period of indifference.

Figure 6

2. This is the case in which the two functions grow **simultaneously** (and, in **Figure 5**, and in many of the subsequent, even with the same **slope**, but it is not always so. Anyhow even in case of different slopes and even in the case of more general functions most observations in this regard remain valid).
3. Then arrive in the situation in which the increase from a part must necessarily be a diminution of the other part (contravariance).

It is necessary at this point, a pause for reflection to emphasize first that this is the situation which is usually regarded as the most frequent. The so-called "realism" especially in foreign policy (*mors tua vita mea*). But it is also necessary to stress that the situations of covariance (or interest) are almost never taken into account, except in **Case A** of **Figure 5**, which is rightly considered trivial and purely ideal.

In common thinking either you do agree or you have to fight. Or you have to have totally separate interests.

Note that even in the "conflict theory" there is no complete clarity on this point (*Galtung J., 1996*). However, this should not be surprising because, actually, even in light of what is being discussed here, the situation is not as intuitive as it might seem at first glance, a demonstration by the fact of how one do not commonly have an adequate operational awareness in these situations.

4. The path then continues with the portion 4, which corresponds to a further second situation always of covariance (albeit declining);
5. and finally we have another stage, number 5, which we also called, for the sake of symmetry, of "indifference."

In reality, in this and in all other cases, the path of exploration of the "space of *decisions*" (in practice simply the interval of the horizontal axis) need not necessarily follow neatly the horizontal axis from left to right, as here assumed for simplicity, but the decision can swing on this axis in an arbitrary manner making us get exactly the same results (as long as it spans at least the whole range).

To sum up: what is important to understand is simply what happens when we move along the horizontal axis, ie how to change the relationship between values (the decision) on both sides to change the decision.

The Case C of Figures 7, which is characterized by a cycle more restricted and that we in fact called cycle collapsed, is very attractive.

It is interesting because it reflects what the common thought is thought to be the only possible solution, namely that of a dyad concerning:

- or the conflict of interests necessarily opposed to" extreme mors your life mea,

or

- the indifference ie the indifference to the consequences of its action, both to the other inner needs, in the case of dilemma or the needs of the other, in the case of a dispute.

Figure 7

This Case C of **Figure 7** is not hence the only possible one as we have shown (there will still be illustrated also other variants shortly: Case C1 of **Figure 8** and Case D of **Figure 9**) and is also important in the light Case B because, in the common thinking, as has been said, there is usually no operational awareness of the covariance situations that is, of the branches 2 and 4 which nevertheless represent real situations.

Through the Case C1 of **Figure 8** that derives from a further distancing of the alternatives and / or by a narrowing of the uncertainty we arrive at the Case D in **Figure 9** which is the case of pure indifference.

Once illustrated in this way the general metaphor, you can go into detail of more purely philosophical reasoning and can reflect on how, in effect, a situation such as that of **Figure 1** (but also for most of the situations of **Figure 8**) involves necessarily and inevitably a dissatisfaction of both parties in any situation where one tries to mediate.

Note that the term *mediation* implies, also geometrically, a decision that lies somewhere in between.

But in the middle there is nothing in these cases! In the middle of two locations that have no uncertainty (**Figure 1**) (or whose uncertainties are "separate" **Figure 9**) there is only a desolate "no man's land" in which every mediation is sterile because it lacks value for both parties

Checking the fourth implicit assumption - is it really true that virtue is always in the middle?

At this point we can go and see, as announced at the beginning, if it is really true that virtue is always in the middle.

To do this we must abandon for a moment the symmetry of the functions hitherto used and utilize someone who is not symmetrical with respect to the maximum value (more precisely, non-symmetrical relative to the axis passing through the maximum value and perpendicular to the axis of decisions).

In addition, so far we have not given any criteria or algorithm to find the decision. Have implicitly assumed that any decision goes well. In fact there is no absolute criterion to determine which is the best decision.

Indeed, the position that has been adopted here is not really to provide such criteria or algorithms, but rather to provide tools for the evaluation of decisions also considering, and this is a very important point and qualifying the relationship between the values (for different subjects or for different points of view) of the decisions. This position implies that a decision is never good in itself, but for its evaluation, it is necessary to take into account the value that this decision also for all the other parties involved.

For reasons of space, we can here only mention the fact that this point is so important that it has been at the center of John Forbes Nash (*Nash J., 1996*).

Just to see if the power really is always in the middle, we do, however, the idea of using an algorithm for the decision. We then discuss some consequences of the adoption of this algorithm in a certain context, date value functions decisions.

Such an algorithm can be, for example but not necessarily, the one called the calculation of the centroid (x_0) the details of which require knowledge of integral calculus as mentioned in Figures 10a and 10b. It is not necessary, however, to know in order to verify with simple means, and the magnitude of all, the validity of the below stated. In fact, just cut out of cardboard figures 10, 11, 12 and 13 and try to make them keep their balance on a knife blade positioned at the bottom of the cardboard and in correspondence of the line passing

Primo Significato del valore di ascissa x_0
(detto *centroide*)

Quel x_0 tale che i momenti alla sua sx ed alla sua ds di si equivalgano

$$\int_{x_1}^{x_0} x f(x) dx = \int_{x_0}^{x_2} x f(x) dx$$

Figure 10a

Secondo Significato del valore di ascissa x_0
(detto *centroide*)

Quel x_0 tale che se vi concentro tutta la "massa" ottengo lo stesso momento della massa distribuita sull'intervallo $[x_1, x_2]$

$$x_0 \int_{x_1}^{x_2} f(x) dx = \int_{x_1}^{x_2} x f(x) dx$$

Figure 10b

through the point x_0 .

The first observation that can be made, observing **Figure 10**, is that the centroid, that is, the point of balance, does not match in this case, contrary to what happened in all the cases examined above, the maximum *value* of the function. In simple words we can say that is not necessarily a balanced *decision* automatically lead to the best *interest* of the *person* who take it. For even better clarify this point, non-intuitive, we analyze a bit 'more in detail the meaning of the function *value* of the decision, in this specific situation. In this case, the *interest*, so to speak, expands more to the left or to the right of the maximum *value*. Recall that at the right hand there is the maximum *value* of the function *value* relative to the other *subject*. In more discursive terms we can say that in this situation our *interest* decreases very rapidly towards a decision that may be of interest also for the other *party* and instead decreases more slowly towards a *decision* in the opposite direction. In the event that there is a proposal for a decision by the other person you are in a situation seemingly paradoxical, for which, while being consistent with its definition of interest in the neighborhood of the maximum, if you want to take a balanced decision must be asked to the left of the maximum and therefore content with a value less than this.

Virtue is really always in the middle? - 2

Figure 11

Vice versa (**Figures 11 and 12**) if and only if I have **proposals** for *decisions* by the **other person** I can make a decision that is both balanced and go more towards (**Figure 11**) or even coincide (**Figure 12**) with my own best interest .

And this is because (and here is the apparent paradox with respect to at least some common sense) I keep into account the proposal of the **other person** and not vice versa. **The other as an opportunity and not as a problem.**

Furthermore, not only in this way I get the most *value* possible for me but I can at the same time and therefore make a satisfaction, albeit marginal, of the other *subject*.

If the proposal then the other *person* has even more weight, the balanced *decision* moves further to the right (ie to him), thus reducing the *interest* on my part.

Note that, however, (**Figures 13**), also in the case in which the second *subject* propose its *decision* with the maximum possible weight, a balanced *decision* can not get to the point of intersection in which the *interests* coincide.

It is interesting to note in this regard as the Latin proverb is ambiguous with respect to what he means exactly by "half." In fact, there are at least two interpretations.

- The medium is the point that is equidistant between the two proposals.
- The medium is the point at which *interests* coincide

In **Figure 13**, for example, these two definitions do not coincide with each other (nor coincide with the calculation of the centroid).

In all the figures prior to the point at which *interests* coincide has been indicated with a gray circle at the intersection of the descending segment of the function **A** with increasing function of **B**.

We can summarize then observing how a balanced *decision* does not necessarily reside in the middle between two proposed *decisions* (either of the two previous definitions is adopted). Indeed even, as shown in **Figure 10**, may well reside fact often outside the range between the two *decisions*. Also, the definition of "medium" is not unique.

The fourth implicit assumption is therefore not always verified.

A new approach to decision making?

The algorithmic criterion (eg. the centroid), however, is not the only one that can guide us in the choice of a solution. We may now show how it is possible to think of a philosophically different approach and which ultimately is the criterion based on the "evaluation of the **consequences**" of a given *decision*. In practice, rather than globally taking into account the uncertainties described by the value functions of the *decisions*, we may seek, among the

Figure 12

Figure 13

Figure 14

decisions, those that produce values that are considered acceptable, eg by establishing a minimum acceptable *value* for both parties. For an illustration of the procedure we may refer to **Figure 14**. Please note that, due to the approach adopted which makes use of the representation in the *space of the relations* is not necessary to use here the *mathematics of the intervals* (see for example *Chen G., Tat Pham T., 2001*). In fact, given the approach adopted here, one can reduce the study to the one of the **segments** of the cycle, rather than to that of intervals. The latter being necessarily more complicated and, after all, is not necessary here.

Equivalent Decisions

We will now briefly introduce the concept of *equivalence* of certain decisions. The situation is illustrated in **Figure 15**. In fact, it may be noted that, with regard to the uncertainty of a decision, there is not only uncertainty about which decision to take, but also the one, that we may call “of *second order*”, relevant to which decisions to take between two *equivalent* ones. For the particular convex form of the adopted functions there always are two decisions that have the same value for a given *subject*. The only exception being the decision at the maximum value. But which one should one choose between the two? As there is no absolute criterion for the decision, so there is none for discriminating between two equivalent decisions (which we can call *determinations*). They are *equivalent* in the sense defined here in **Figure 15**. However it can be observed that we can get a criterion by evaluating the *value* that a decision, established by an *entity*, has for the **other** entity. This discrimination between two otherwise equivalent determinations, has profound philosophical and practical implications. Essentially it comes to evidence the importance of wondering always whether the decisions that have some *value* for **us**, may also possibly have an *equivalent one* *ideed equivalent for us* but which, however, may have **better** consequences for the **other party**.

In the following are reported, for completeness, other figures (**Figures 16, 17 and 18**) that illustrate other situations of *equivalence* and *independence* showing that, in effect, the “spectrum” of possible decisions, far from being limited solely to the situation of *contravariance* (commonly described by the metaphor of *mors tua vita mea*) is much wider than usually imagined.

For a possible taxonomy of *value* functions see for example *Fortemps P. and M. Roubens, 1996*.

Figure 15

Case B1 - Indifference to the maximum (of a part)

Figure 16

Case B2 - Indifference to the maximum (of both parts)

figure 17

Linearity e Cyclicity

From a systemic *point of view* the most interesting aspect of the approach described here is perhaps the one that reveals the otherwise hidden **cyclical nature** of the process related to the analysis of a *dilemma*.

The result is even more surprising when one notes that, in effect, not only in the light of intuitive observation but also of physiological investigation, experimental evidence indeed suggests an oscillatory pattern, but along a straight line. In fact, even the nystagmus, which is the movement that the human eye follows in assessing two physically present alternatives, is a sudden angular oscillation which, projected on the object, describes a substantially straight trajectory.

This, in the history of philosophy, is metaphorically indicated by the left and right oscillation of the head of *Buridan's ass*.

As we have seen so far it should instead become clear that the oscillatory movement relative to the exploration of *alternatives* implies also a corresponding **circular** motion in the space of relations between the values of the *decisions*.

On the other end, limiting oneself to observe only the **decisions** themselves, regardless of their *value*, the *metaphor* of *Buridan's ass* is in fact still appropriate.

Case B3 – Quadrature
(Indifference to the maximum and the minimum of both parts) Figure 18

Conclusions

The novelty of the *Fuzzy* reasoning (which here simply boils down to assigning a *value* to points in the neighborhood of a certain given *alternative*) is perhaps in having introduced one more dimension: that in fact the value of a *decision* (to a certain *point of view* or for a certain *subject*). This new dimension, in turn, allows to take these *values* and correlate them. This correlation is of a substantially **circular** nature also in the "degenerate" cases of *Figure 5* and *Figure 9*.

Bibliography

All figures are original and created by the author.

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